

Impact of Variable Fluid Properties on Hybrid Nanofluid Flow Over a Stretching Surface with Nonlinear Thermal Radiation

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Abstract—In many technical applications viscosity of fluid varies with respect to temperature, so it is important to understand the dynamics of the fluid under varying fluid properties. This article presents numerical investigation on thermal characteristics of hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching surface considering viscosity, thermal conductivity as function of temperature. The highly nonlinear partial differential equations are converted as equations of single similarity variable using appropriate similarity and then shooting method is employed to solve the model. Copper-alumina oxide nanoparticles are used in this study with base fluid as water. Heat transfer rate is more in hybrid nanofluid model as compared to mono particle based nanofluid with variable thermal conductivity.

Keywords— Heat transfer, Hybrid nanofluid, Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD), Non-Linear thermal radiation, Variable fluid properties

NOMENCLATURE

u,v	Velocity in x and y axis (m s^{-1})	GREEK SYMBOLS	
u_w	Stretching sheet velocity (m s^{-1})	β	Thermal expansion co-efficient
g	Acceleration due to gravity	β_1	Variable viscosity
T	Fluid temperature (K)	β_2	Variable thermal conductivity
T_∞	Ambient temperature (K)	η	Dimensionless similarity variable
T_w	Wall temperature (K)	σ	Electrical conductivity of fluid
C_w	Surface Concentration	σ^*	Stefan Boltzman constant
C_∞	Ambient concentration	k^*	Mean absorption co-efficient
θ	Dimensionless temperature	μ_{hnf}	Viscosity of hybrid nanofluid
a	Stretching rate (s^{-1})	μ_{nf}	Viscosity of nanofluid
θ_w	Temperature ratio parameter	μ_0	Viscosity of fluid
B_0	Induced magnetic field	ρ	Density of fluid
q_r	Radiative heat flux	ρ_{cp}	Heat capacitance
k	Thermal conductivity	ϕ_1	Alumina particles volume fraction
M	Magnetic field parameter	ϕ_2	Copper particles volume fraction
R	Thermal Radiation	SUBSCRIPT	
Pr	Prandtl Number	f	Base fluid
λ	Convection parameter	nf	Nanofluid
K	Heat capacity	hnf	Hybrid nanofluid
		s	Solid
		s1	Alumina
		s2	Copper

I. INTRODUCTION

The boundary layer analysis of nanofluid has been an essential domain of study due to the improved thermal conductivity property of nano-sized particles. Controlled heat transfer management is pivotal in many manufacturing industries, including extrusion processes and electronic devices ^[1]. Hybrid nanofluids

are a new kind of engineered coolant in which more than two nanoparticles are mixed to produce increased heat transfer compared to nanofluids. Ali et al.^[2] assessed heat transfer augmentation with $CuO - TiO_2$ nano particles. The authors considered three types of shape factors in their investigation, and results show that platelet shape nanoparticles are more efficient. Sulochana and Aparna^[3] studied the role of hybrid nanofluid in unsteady liquid thin film flow with Brownian motion effects. They reported that increasing Brownian motion and thermophoresis parameters will drastically reduce the heat exchange rate. Tlili et al.^[4] explored the three-dimensional flow of hybrid nanofluid flow with variable thickness stretching surface. Waini et al.^[5] investigated transpiration impact on stretching/shrinking surfaces. The authors reported that a noticeable heat transfer rate could be achieved with Cu nanoparticles and also identified the existence of dual solutions. The significance of $MgO - CuO$ hybrid nanofluid over two distinct geometries was investigated by Sulochana et al.^[6]. Rashid et al.^[7] theoretically investigated the convective conditions over a stretching sheet, considering silver alumina nanoparticles past a stretching sheet. Recently, Joshi et al.^[8] explored their study on the impact of injection and suction over a hybrid Darcy-Forchheimer nanofluid across a porous stretching surface. They also presented numerically a mixed convective flow of hybrid nanofluid $SWCNT - Ag/H_2O$ with the effect of high chemical reaction and internal heat generation^[9]. Upreti et al.^[10] investigated the effect of heat transfer and entropy generation over squeezed magnetic hybrid nanofluid flow. They considered carbon nanotubes as nanoparticles immersed in the water-EG base fluid and concluded that the entropy generation accelerates with increasing values of magnetic fields. Yusuf et al.^[11] studied Copper and Titanium dioxide nanofluid flow past a three-dimensional stretching surface. They analysed the slip effect considering the porous media and declared that there is more entropy for common nanofluids than hybrid nanofluids.

The heat transfer process is analysed in many industrial applications by studying boundary layer flow with changing fluid properties. Variable viscosity and temperature-dependent thermal conductivity are vital in space technology, plastics, ceramics, pharmaceuticals, and glass fiber. Three-dimensional magnetohydrodynamic flow with H_2 bond is explained by Ghadikolaei and Gholinia,^[12] their results support the claim that $Go - MoS_2$ causes increased temperature trends. Abbas et al.^[13] examined MHD Carreau boundary layer fluid flow across a stretching permeable layer with varying thermal conductivity and viscosity. Shamsuddin and Eid^[14] investigated the variable viscosity and heat conductivity of a magnetized nanofluid flowing from a parallel stretchable rotating disk. Irfan^[15] analysed thermophoretic diffusion and Brownian motion in the nonlinear mixed convection flow of a Carreau nanofluid with changing characteristics. Mandal et al.^[16] evaluated entropy formation and stability analysis along an exponentially diminishing permeable Riga surface over a radiative $Ag - MoS_2$ /water hybrid nanofluid flow with variable viscosity/conductivity. A mathematical examination of MHD hybrid nanofluid movement across a stretching surface under varying slip conditions and viscosity is addressed by Rafique et al.^[17] Variable fluid properties' effects on MHD hybrid nanofluid flow across an exponentially long sheet with uneven heat production are recorded by Manigandan et al.^[18]. Mahmood et al.^[19] investigated a hybrid nanofluid's mixed convective stagnation point flow over a sheet with varying slip conditions and thermal conductivity. A numerical study of MHD Carreau hybrid nanofluid flow across a stretching sheet in a porous media with viscosity changes and heat transfer is examined by Alkawasbeh et al.^[20]. Karthik et al.^[21] evaluated double diffusive on Powell Eyring fluid flow from an exponential stretching surface with varying thermal conductivity and viscosity through mixed convection.

Temperature dissimilarities between the surface of the hot body and free stream fluid cause a density gradient in fluid flow. However, most authors discussed hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching sheet problem, considering constant viscosity, constant thermal conductivity, and heat transfer phenomena with nonlinear thermal radiation in hybrid nanofluids, which are scant. Hence, the primary aim of this article is to present the thermos-physical properties of $Cu - Al_2O_3/H_2O$ with varying fluid properties with nonlinear thermal radiation effect. As far as we know, no prior reports of this kind of work in boundary layer flow problems exist. The present work is very close to the works of Manjunatha et al.^[22], Yashkun et al.^[23], and Venkateswarlu^[24]. but the variable conductivity model and thermal radiation effect are entirely different from the studies mentioned above. The results of this investigation are beneficial to understanding heat transport phenomena in many industrial applications where viscosity varies with respect to temperature.

II. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

We examine a steady, incompressible, laminar hybrid nanofluid flow in two dimensions (2D) across a stretching surface. Flow is restricted to $y > 0$ and parallel to the plane $y=0$. Keep the origin fixed and stretch the sheet with velocity $U_w(x) = ax$, $a > 0$. Transverse magnetic field B_0 is applied normal to stretching surface. Geometrical depiction of the tangible model and reference frame is shown in physical model. With these assumptions, the governing equations of boundary layer flow are given by (See [25], [26]).

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$\rho_{hnf} \left\{ u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right\} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\mu_{hnf}(T) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) + g(\rho\beta)_{hnf}(T - T_\infty) - \sigma_{hnf} B_0^2 u \tag{2}$$

$$(\rho c_p)_{hnf} \left\{ u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right\} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[k_{hnf}(T) \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} - q_r \right] \tag{3}$$

corresponding boundary conditions are taken as

$$u = U_w, v = 0, T = T_w \text{ at } y = 0 \text{ and } u \rightarrow 0, T \rightarrow T_\infty \text{ as } y \rightarrow \infty \tag{4}$$

Specifically, u and v represent the velocity components along the directions x and y . U_w indicates velocity at the wall, T_w is wall temperature, T_∞ free stream temperature, by Rosseland approximation, q_r radiative heat flux (Wm^{-2}) [27] becomes

$$q_r = \frac{-4\sigma^*}{3K^*} \frac{\partial T^4}{\partial y} = \frac{-16\sigma^*}{3K^*} T^3 \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}, \text{ here } T = T_\infty \{1 + (\theta_w - 1)\theta\}, \text{ where } \theta_w = \frac{T_w}{T_\infty}$$

Fig. 1 Physical model of fluid flow

The varying thermal conductivity relation [28], [29] with respect to temperature is given by

$$k_{hnf} = k_f (1 + \beta_2 \theta(\eta)) \tag{5}$$

and viscosity is considered as function of temperature $\mu_f = \mu_0 e^{-\beta_1 \theta}$, where β_1 is variable viscosity parameter [22], [30].

Introducing similarity transformations [31]

$$\eta = \sqrt{\frac{a}{\nu_f}} y, \quad u = ax f'(\eta), \quad v = -\sqrt{a\nu_f} f(\eta), \quad \theta = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty} \tag{6}$$

With introduction of similarity variables in (6) the governing equations (2)-(4) are reshaped in non-dimensional form as

$$f''' + A_1 A_2 (f f'' - f'^2) + \lambda A_2 A_3 \theta - \beta_1 f'' \theta' - A_2 M f' = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$\left[\frac{k_{hnf}}{k_f} \right] \theta'' + \frac{4R}{3} \left((1 + \theta(\theta_w - 1))^3 \theta' \right)' + \beta_2 \theta \theta'' + \beta_2 (\theta')^2 = 0 \tag{8}$$

and the boundary condition will be

$$f(0) = 0, f'(0) = 1, \theta(0) = 1, f'(\infty) = 0, \theta(\infty) = 0 \quad \#(9)$$

Where

$$A_1 = \left[1 - \phi_2 \left\{ (1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \left(\frac{\rho_{s1}}{\rho_f} \right) \right\} + \phi_2 \left(\frac{\rho_{s2}}{\rho_f} \right) \right]$$

$$A_2 = [(1 - \phi_1)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_2)^{2.5}]$$

$$A_3 = \left[1 - \phi_2 \left\{ (1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \left(\frac{(\rho\beta)_{s1}}{(\rho\beta)_f} \right) \right\} + \phi_2 \left(\frac{(\rho\beta)_{s2}}{(\rho\beta)_f} \right) \right]$$

Dimensionless parameters for Prandtl number, Radiation parameter, Magnetic parameter, Convection parameter are

$$Pr = \frac{v_f(\rho c_p)_{hnf}}{k_f}, \quad R = \frac{4\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{3K^* k_f}, \quad M = \frac{\sigma_{hnf} B_0^2}{a \rho_f}, \quad \lambda = \frac{g \beta_f T_w - T_\infty}{a^2 x} \quad \#(10)$$

Table I. Thermo physical features of nano particles and base fluid [32], [33]

Type of particle	$\rho(kg/m^3)$	$C_p(J/kgK)$	$k(W/mK)$	$\beta(K^{-1})$
Cu	8933	385	400	0.0000765
Al_2O_3	3970	765	40	0.000051
H_2O	997.1	4179	0.613	0.000256

Table II. Correlations for thermo physical properties [32], [33]

Property	Nanofluid	Hybrid nanofluid
Viscosity $(Ns/m^2)(\mu)$	$\frac{\mu_f}{(1 - \phi_2)^{2.5}}$	$\frac{\mu_f}{(1 - \phi_1)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_2)^{2.5}}$
Density $(kg/m^3)(\rho)$	$(1 - \phi_2)\rho_f + \phi_2\rho_s$	$(1 - \phi_2)\{(1 - \phi_1)\rho_f + \phi_1\rho_{s1}\} + \phi_2\rho_{s2}$
Heat Capacity $(J/kg K)(\rho c_p)$	$(1 - \phi_2)\{(1 - \phi_1)(\rho c_p)_f + \phi_1(\rho c_p)_s\} + \phi_2(\rho c_p)_{s2}$	$(1 - \phi_2)\{(1 - \phi_1)(\rho c_p)_f + \phi_1(\rho c_p)_{s1}\} + \phi_2(\rho c_p)_{s2}$
Thermal conductivity $(W/m K)(k)$	$\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} = \frac{k_s + (m - 1)k_f - (m - 1)\phi_2(k_f - k_s)}{k_s + (m - 1)k_f + \phi_2(k_f - k_s)}$	$\frac{k_{hnf}}{k_f} = \frac{k_{s2} + (m - 1)k_{bf} - (m - 1)\phi_2(k_{bf} - k_{s2})}{k_{s2} + (m - 1)k_{bf} + (m - 1)\phi_2(k_{bf} - k_{s2})}$ Where $\frac{k_{bf}}{k_f} = \frac{k_{s1} + (m - 1)k_f - (m - 1)\phi_1(k_f - k_{s1})}{k_{s1} + (m - 1)k_f + (m - 1)\phi_1(k_f - k_{s1})}$
Thermal expansion coefficient $\beta(K^{-1})$	$(1 - \phi_2)\beta_f + \phi_2\beta_s$	$(1 - \phi_2)\{(1 - \phi_1)\beta_f + \phi_1\beta_{s1}\} + \phi_2\beta_{s2}$

The surface drag (Skin friction coefficient) and rate of heat transfer (Nusselt number) are computed as

$$C_f = \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\rho_f u_w^2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0} \quad \text{and} \quad Nu_x = \frac{-x k_{hnf}}{k_f (T_w - T_\infty)} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}$$

non-dimensional form of these two quantities using similarity transformation as in equation (6) are

$$C_f Re_x^{\frac{-1}{2}} = - \frac{1}{(1 - \phi_1)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_2)^{2.5}} f''(0)$$

$$Nu_x Re_x^{\frac{-1}{2}} = - \left[\frac{k_{hnf}}{k_f} + \frac{4R}{3} (1 + \theta(0)(\theta_w - 1))^3 \right] \theta'(0)$$

III. NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

In order to analyse the solution of highly nonlinear ODEs mentioned by equations (7), (8) and (9) with boundary conditions, are solved numerically for differing values of the governing parameters using the BVP4c shooting technique. Transforming the boundary value problem into initial value problem then solved by a systematic guessing for $f''(0)$ and $\theta'(0)$ as long as the far field condition for the boundary is met. The accuracy of the solution is attained to 10^{-6} .

$$f = y_1, \quad f' = y_2, \quad f'' = y_3, \quad \theta = y_4, \quad \theta' = y_5.$$

$$y_3' = A_2 M y_2 - A_1 A_2 (y_1 y_3 - y_2^2) - \lambda A_2 A_3 y_4 + \beta_1 y_3 y_5$$

$$y_5' = \frac{1}{P_r} \left[\frac{k_{hnf}}{k_f} \right] \left\{ \frac{-4R}{3} [1 + y_4 (\theta_w - 1)^3 y_5]' - \beta_2 y_4 y_5' - \beta_2 (y_5)^2 \right\}$$

boundary conditions are

$$Ya(1)-0, \quad ya(2)-1, \quad ya(4)-1, \quad yb(2)-0, \quad yb(4)-0$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The current investigation addresses the detailed explanation about the impact of distinct parameters on momentum, temperature profiles. The mathematical model is represented by governing equations (7)-(8) with boundary conditions (9) in dimensionless form are solved by applying shooting method. The values of physical parameters are considered in the ranges $0 \leq M \leq 3$, $0 \leq R \leq 2$, $0 \leq \phi_1 \leq 0.01$, $0 \leq \phi_2 \leq 0.04$, $0 \leq \beta_1 \leq 4$, $0 \leq \beta_2 \leq 1$, $\eta_\infty = 4$ for computing the results. Table 1 indicates the thermophysical values of the base fluid and nanoparticles such as, density (ρ), specific heat (c_p), thermal conductivity (k), thermal expansion coefficient β . Table 2 demonstrates the thermophysical characteristics of nanofluid and hybrid nanofluid. Table 3 displays the comparison of our present work with earlier presented work.

The influence of magnetic field strength (M) on momentum is shown in Figure 2 and it is clear that velocity reduction takes place for higher M values because of the (opposing force) Lorentz force. Controlling velocity by applying a magnetic field has a wide range of industrial applications, like the electromagnetic coating of metals and wires, etc. The effect of M on temperature distribution is depicted in Figure 3 Greater values of M cause the fluid's density to decrease, and as a result, there is a rise in temperature. The impact of the variable viscosity parameter (β_1) over the velocity distribution is as displayed in Figure 4 where it is observed that momentum decreases with increasing viscosity parameter values. The significance of the mixed convection parameter on momentum and temperature distributions is visualized in Figure 5 and Figure 6. Physically $\lambda > 0$ indicates cooling of the surface, and $\lambda < 0$ denotes heating of the surface. Figure 5 shows that the mixed convection parameter (λ) accelerates velocity profile, with the reason for this behaviour being the difference between surface temperature T_w and free stream temperature T_∞ . From figure 7 and figure 8 it is observed that both velocity and temperature profiles enhance for rising β_2 .

The skin friction coefficient for the variable viscosity term in the presence of a magnetic field is shown in Figure 9. Higher values of the viscosity parameter (β_1) are found to result in increased skin friction. The Nusselt number for variable viscosity is plotted in Figure 10 and declining profile is noticed. Table 4 presents the skin friction coefficient and Nusselt number values computed for various physical factors. Figure 11-12 illustrate the effect of the variable thermal conductivity factor (β_2) on the surface drag function and local Nusselt number, respectively. It has been found that nanofluids based on single particles have a lower surface drag coefficient than hybrid nanofluids, and similar behavior is seen in the case of the Nusselt number in relation to the variable thermal conductivity parameter. A key role is played by the nanoparticle volume fraction in determining the optimum heat transfer rate. The role of the nanoparticle volume fraction (ϕ_2) on the surface drag function is depicted in Figure 13 and Nusselt number for nanoparticle volume fraction is depicted in Figure 14. The skin friction coefficient rises as the volume fraction of nanoparticles grows, whereas the opposite behaviour is noticed in the Nusselt number for nanoparticle volume fraction.

Table III. Comparison of numerical outcomes of $-\theta'(0)$ for varying Pr values when $\phi_1 = \phi_2 = B = M = \lambda = 0$

Pr	Manjunatha et al. [22][22][22]	Present results
2.0	0.9113	0.91135
6.13	-	1.75968
7.0	1.8954	1.89540
20.0	1.3539	1.35390

Table IV. Values of the skin friction coefficient and Nusselt number for various physical parameters

M	R	λ	θ_w	$C_f Re_x^{-\frac{1}{2}}$		$Nu_x Re_x^{-\frac{1}{2}}$	
				Nanofluid	Hybrid Nanofluid	Nanofluid	Hybrid Nanofluid
0.5				1.09128	1.07789	2.06678	2.16170
1.0				1.28927	1.28451	1.96879	2.07040
1.5				1.46624	1.47074	1.88535	1.99094
	1			1.36039	1.30200	1.56162	1.65170
	1.2			1.29624	1.29298	1.76785	1.86370
	1.4			1.28927	1.28451	1.96879	2.07040
		0.2		1.50401	1.56247	1.82495	1.88113
		0.4		1.35943	1.37644	1.92534	1.99611
		0.6		1.22028	1.19831	2.00880	2.08984
			1.3	1.29154	1.28915	1.28915	1.73097
			1.6	1.28440	1.28094	1.28094	2.81506
			1.9	1.27639	1.27172	1.27172	4.35889

Fig. 2 Influence of magnetic field on momentum profile

Fig. 3 Influence of magnetic field on temperature profile

Fig. 4 Influence of variable viscosity parameter on velocity.

Fig. 5 Influence of convection parameter on velocity

Fig. 6 Impact of convection parameter on temperature profile

Fig. 7 Impact of variable conductivity parameter on momentum

Fig. 8 Impact of variable conductivity parameter on temperature profile

Fig. 9 Skin friction coefficient for variable viscosity parameter

Fig. 10 Nusselt number for variable viscosity parameter

Fig. 11 Skin friction for variable thermal conductivity parameter

Fig. 12 Nusselt number for variable thermal conductivity parameter

Fig. 13 Skin friction for nano particle volume fraction

Fig. 14 Nusselt number for nano particle volume fraction

V. CONCLUSIONS

Boundary layer flow of hybrid nanofluid over a stretching sheet with variable fluid properties is simulated numerically using shooting method. Some of the important points observed in this study are:

- Nusselt number and Skin friction coefficient of hybrid nanofluid is greater than nanofluid with variable thermal conductivity.
- Nusselt number diminishes with temperature dependent variable viscosity parameter.
- Skin friction increases with temperature dependent variable viscosity.
- Temperature profiles and momentum are increased with parameter variable thermal conductivity for nanofluid and hybrid nanofluid

Conflict of interests

Authors have no conflict of interests.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. R. Eid and M. A. Nafe, "Thermal conductivity variation and heat generation effects on magneto-hybrid nanofluid flow in a porous medium with slip condition," *Waves in Random and Complex Media*, vol. Vol. 32, no. No. 3, pp. 1103–1127, 2022, doi: 10.1080/17455030.2020.1810365.
- [2] A. Ali, S. Saleem, S. Mumraiz, A. Saleem, M. Awais, and D. N. Khan Marwat, "Investigation on TiO₂-Cu/H₂O hybrid nanofluid with slip conditions in MHD peristaltic flow of Jeffrey material," *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.*, vol. Vol. 143, no. No. 3, pp. 1985–1996, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10973-020-09648-1.
- [3] C. Sulochana and S. R. Aparna, "Unsteady magnetohydrodynamic radiative liquid thin film flow of hybrid nanofluid with thermophoresis and Brownian motion," *Multidiscip. Model. Mater. Struct.*, vol. Vol. 16, no. No. 4, pp. 811–834, 2020, doi: 10.1108/MMMS-08-2019-0160.
- [4] I. Tlili, H. A. Nabwey, G. P. Ashwinkumar, and N. Sandeep, "3-D magnetohydrodynamic AA7072-AA7075/methanol hybrid nanofluid flow above an uneven thickness surface with slip effect," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. Vol. 10, no. No. 1, pp. 1–13, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-61215-8.
- [5] I. Waini, A. Ishak, and I. Pop, "Transpiration effects on hybrid nanofluid flow and heat transfer over a stretching/shrinking sheet with uniform shear flow," *Alexandria Eng. J.*, vol. Vol. 59, no. No. 1, pp. 91–99, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2019.12.010.

- [6] C. Sulochana, S. R. Aparna, and N. Sandeep, "Magnetohydrodynamic MgO/CuO-water hybrid nanofluid flow driven by two distinct geometries," *Heat Transf.*, vol. Vol. 49, no. No. 6, pp. 3663–3682, 2020, doi: 10.1002/htj.21794.
- [7] A. Rashid, M. Ayaz, S. Islam, A. Saeed, and P. Kumam, "South African Journal of Chemical Engineering Theoretical analysis of the MHD flow of a tangent hyperbolic hybrid nanofluid over a stretching sheet with convective conditions : A nonlinear thermal radiation case," *South African J. Chem. Eng.*, vol. Vol. 42, no. July, pp. 255–269, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.sajce.2022.09.005.
- [8] N. Joshi, H. Upreti, and A. K. Pandey, "MHD Darcy-Forchheimer Cu-Ag/H₂O-C₂H₆O₂ hybrid nanofluid flow via a porous stretching sheet with suction/blowing and viscous dissipation," *Int. J. Comput. Methods Eng. Sci. Mech.*, vol. Vol. 23, no. No. 6, p. pp. 527-535, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1080/15502287.2022.2030426.
- [9] N. Joshi, "Mixed convection flow of magnetic hybrid nanofluid over a bidirectional porous surface with internal heat generation and a higher - order chemical reaction," *heat Transf.*, vol. Vol. 50, no. September 2020, pp. 3661–3682, 2021, doi: 10.1002/htj.22046.
- [10] H. Upreti, A. K. Pandey, and M. Kumar, "Unsteady squeezing flow of magnetic hybrid nanofluids within parallel plates and entropy generation," *Heat Transf.*, vol. Vol. 50, no. August 2020, pp. 105–125, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1002/htj.21994.
- [11] T. A. Yusuf, F. Mabood, W. A. Khan, and J. A. Gbadeyan, "Irreversibility analysis of Cu-TiO₂-H₂O hybrid-nanofluid impinging on a 3-D stretching sheet in a porous medium with nonlinear radiation: Darcy-Forchheimer's model," *Alexandria Eng. J.*, vol. Vol. 59, no. No. 6, pp. 5247–5261, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2020.09.053.
- [12] S. S. Ghadikolaei and M. Gholinia, "3D mixed convection MHD flow of GO-MoS₂ hybrid nanoparticles in H₂O-(CH₂OH)₂ hybrid base fluid under the effect of H₂ bond," *Int. Commun. Heat Mass Transf.*, vol. Vol. 110, p. 104371, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.icheatmasstransfer.2019.104371.
- [13] T. Abbas, S. Rehman, R. A. Shah, M. Idrees, and M. Qayyum, "Analysis of MHD Carreau fluid flow over a stretching permeable sheet with variable viscosity and thermal conductivity," *Phys. A Stat. Mech. its Appl.*, vol. 551, p. 124225, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physa.2020.124225>.
- [14] M. D. Shamshuddin and M. R. Eid, "Magnetized nanofluid flow of ferromagnetic nanoparticles from parallel stretchable rotating disk with variable viscosity and thermal conductivity," *Chinese J. Phys.*, vol. 74, pp. 20–37, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjph.2021.07.038>.
- [15] M. Irfan, "Study of Brownian motion and thermophoretic diffusion on non-linear mixed convection flow of Carreau nanofluid subject to variable properties," *Surfaces and Interfaces*, vol. 23, p. 100926, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2021.100926>.
- [16] G. Mandal and D. Pal, "Dual solutions of radiative Ag-MoS₂/water hybrid nanofluid flow with variable viscosity and variable thermal conductivity along an exponentially shrinking permeable Riga surface: Stability and entropy generation analysis," *Int. J. Model. Simul.*, vol. 0, no. 0, pp. 1–26, 2023, doi: 10.1080/02286203.2023.2171656.
- [17] K. Rafique, Z. Mahmood, and U. Khan, "Mathematical analysis of MHD hybrid nanofluid flow with variable viscosity and slip conditions over a stretching surface," *Mater. Today Commun.*, vol. 36, p. 106692, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2023.106692>.
- [18] A. Manigandan and P. V. Satya Narayana, "Impact of variable fluid characteristics on MHD hybrid nanofluid (MgO+ZnO/H₂O) flow over an exponentially elongated sheet with non-uniform heat generation," *Case Stud. Therm. Eng.*, vol. 55, p. 104077, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2024.104077>.
- [19] Z. Mahmood, K. Rafique, U. Khan, Adnan, M. Abd El-Rahman, and R. Alharbi, "Analysis of mixed convective stagnation point flow of hybrid nanofluid over sheet with variable thermal conductivity and slip Conditions: A Model-Based study," *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow*, vol. 106, p. 109296, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatfluidflow.2024.109296>.
- [20] H. T. Alkasasbeh, "Numerical Investigation of MHD Carreau Hybrid Nanofluid Flow over a Stretching Sheet in a Porous Medium with Viscosity Variations and Heat Transport," *J. Comput. Appl. Mech.*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 410–424, 2023, doi: 10.22059/jcamech.2023.364255.861.
- [21] S. Karthik, D. Iranian, H. Alhazmi, I. Khan, A. Singh, and M. I. Khan, "Double diffusive on powell eyring fluid flow by mixed convection from an exponential stretching surface with variable viscosity/thermal conductivity," *Case Stud. Therm. Eng.*, vol. 55, p. 104091, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2024.104091>.
- [22] S. Manjunatha, B. Ammani Kuttan, S. Jayanthi, A. Chamkha, and B. J. Gireesha, "Heat transfer enhancement in the boundary layer flow of hybrid nanofluids due to variable viscosity and natural convection," *Heliyon*, vol. Vol. 5, no. No. 4, p. e01469, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01469.
- [23] U. Yashkun, K. Zaimi, N. A. Abu Bakar, A. Ishak, and I. Pop, "MHD hybrid nanofluid flow over a permeable stretching/shrinking sheet with thermal radiation effect," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Heat Fluid Flow*, vol. Vol. 31, no. No. 3, pp. 1014–1031, 2021, doi: 10.1108/HFF-02-2020-0083.
- [24] B. Venkateswarlu and P. V. Satya Narayana, "Cu-Al₂O₃/H₂O hybrid nanofluid flow past a porous stretching sheet due to temperatue-dependent viscosity and viscous dissipation," *Heat Transf.*, vol. Vol. 50, no. No. 1, pp. 432–449, 2021, doi: 10.1002/htj.21884.
- [25] N. S. Akbar and Z. H. Khan, "Effect of variable thermal conductivity and thermal radiation with CNTS suspended nanofluid over a stretching sheet with convective slip boundary conditions: Numerical study," *J. Mol. Liq.*, vol. Vol. 222, p. pp.279-286, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.molliq.2016.06.102.
- [26] J. A. Gbadeyan, E. O. Titiloye, and A. T. Adeosun, "Effect of variable thermal conductivity and viscosity on Casson nanofluid flow with convective heating and velocity slip," *Heliyon*, vol. Vol. 6, no. No. 1, p. e03076, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e03076.
- [27] N. Acharya, R. Bag, and P. Kumar, "On the impact of nonlinear thermal radiation on magnetized hybrid condensed nanofluid flow over a permeable texture," *Appl. Nanosci.*, vol. Vol. 10, no. No. 0123456789, p. pp 1679–1691, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s13204-019-01224-w.

- [28] T. C. Chiam, "Heat transfer in a fluid with variable thermal conductivity over a linearly stretching sheet," *Acta Mech.*, vol. Vol. 129, no. No. 1-2, pp. 63–72, 1998, doi: 10.1007/BF01379650.
- [29] M. Usman, M. Hamid, T. Zubair, R. Ul Haq, and W. Wang, "Cu-Al₂O₃/Water hybrid nanofluid through a permeable surface in the presence of nonlinear radiation and variable thermal conductivity via LSM," *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.*, vol. vol 126, p. pp.1347-1356, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2018.06.005.
- [30] S. Manjunatha, V. Puneeth, B. J. Giresha, and A. J. Chamkha, "Theoretical Study of Convective Heat Transfer in Ternary Nanofluid Flowing past a Stretching Sheet," *J. Appl. Comput. Mech.*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1279–1286, 2022, doi: 10.22055/JACM.2021.37698.3067.
- [31] S. Naramgari and C. Sulochana, "MHD flow over a permeable stretching/shrinking sheet of a nanofluid with suction/injection," *Alexandria Eng. J.*, vol. Vol. 55, no. No. 2, pp. 819–827, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2016.02.001.
- [32] H. F. Oztop and E. Abu-Nada, "Numerical study of natural convection in partially heated rectangular enclosures filled with nanofluids," *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow*, vol. Vol. 29, no. No. 5, pp. 1326–1336, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.ijheatfluidflow.2008.04.009.
- [33] I. Waini, A. Ishak, and I. Pop, "Flow and heat transfer along a permeable stretching/shrinking curved surface in a hybrid nanofluid," *Phys. Scr.*, vol. Vol. 94, no. No.10, p. 104565, 2019, doi: 10.1088/1402-4896/ab0fd5.